

Reactivity of benzo[b]furans: A full perspective

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Vahideh Zadsirjan, Mahzad Dehghani

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Benzofuran derivatives and benzofurans are presented as scaffolds in complex molecules and have attracted much attention and prevalent interest due to their interesting biological activity. They also exist in several numbers of naturally occurring compounds and exhibiting biological activity. In this review, we will try to underscore the reactivity of benzofurans through comprehension and giving a full perspective to the readers.

Keywords

Benzo[b]furan, Biological activity, Reactivity